

A three-dimensional coordination polymer of cobalt(II) dicyanamide containing an *in situ* generated didentate Schiff base : Synthesis, structure and magnetic property

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Abstract : One 3D coordination polymer of cobalt(II) dicyanamide of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2]_n$ (**1**) (L = phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methanimine, dca = dicyanamide) has been isolated using a 1 : 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine (ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and Na(dca) respectively in alcoholic solvent at room temperature. Single crystal X-ray crystallographic analysis shows that **1** crystallizes in the orthorhombic unit cell, space group P2(1)2(1)2(1) with unit cell dimensions, $a = 8.506(5)$ Å, $b = 12.736(7)$ Å, $c = 15.635(9)$ Å and $\beta = 90^\circ$. Each cobalt(II) center in **1** adopts a distorted octahedral geometry with CoN_6 chromophore coordinated by two N atoms of didentate Schiff base and four nitrile N atoms of four different dca units. **1** affords a 3D network structure where four $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridges connect four different metal(II) centers. Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement of **1** shows weak antiferromagnetic coupling among the cobalt(II) centers mediated through $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridges. The compound exhibits $(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence in solid states at room temperature.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) coordination polymer, *in situ* generated Schiff base, dicyanamide, X-ray structure, antiferromagnetism, luminescence.

Introduction

Synthesis^{1,2} of mono-, di- and polynuclear coordination molecules of cobalt(II) has received great interest due to their interesting synthetic, structural, spectroscopic and magnetic features³⁻⁶. One-pot reaction of the building components such as metal ions, organic end-capping ligands and inorganic/organic terminals/bridges with judiciously chosen molar ratios is one of the efficient synthetic approaches to isolate compounds with tunable properties. Schiff bases⁷ are often used as organic spacers because of their ease of preparation, structural variety, varied denticity and subtle steric and/or electronic effects controlling molecular aggregates and crystalline architectures. In contrast, syntheses invoking *in situ* unusual ligand preparation^{8,9} in presence of different metal ions, which are very much efficient for the isolation of stable metal-

organic frameworks (MOFs) with exciting properties, are rare. Dicyanamide (dca), a larger pseudohalide molecular ion-rod^{10,11} is under active consideration as bridging unit primarily due to interesting extended architectures and related properties in metal bound states. Keeping in mind the various *in situ* preparation of Schiff bases, we wish to study such reaction in presence of cobalt(II) in combination with dicyanamide. Successfully, we have isolated one 3D coordination polymer poly[phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methanimine-di- μ -dicyanamidocobalt(II)], $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2]_n$ (**1**) (L = phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methanimine, dca = dicyanamide) using a 1 : 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine (ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and Na(dca) in alcoholic solvent at room temperature. X-Ray structural study reveals that in the condensation reaction of ap and bp some degradation

occurs to afford a didentate Schiff base (L, Scheme 1). The details of synthesis, spectroscopic results, X-ray structure, magnetic property and luminescence behavior of this complex are described below.

Scheme 1. Framework of the didentate Schiff base (L).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The coordination polymer $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2]_n$ (**1**) was obtained by the reaction of a 1 : 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine (ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and Na(dca) in MeOH solvent at room temperature. A condensation reaction between ap and bp followed by a degradation process in presence of cobalt(II) occurs to afford a didentate Schiff base L in **1**. X-Ray structural analysis confirms this proposition. The reaction is reproducible, as is evident from repetitive microanalytical and spectral results. The reproducibility reflects an inherent tendency towards formation of the complex **1**. The reaction is summarized in eq. (1) :

The new complex was characterized by microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physico-chemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulation **1**. The moisture-insensitive compound is stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states. It is soluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. In MeCN solution **1** behaves a non-electrolyte, as reflected from its low conductivity value ($7 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)¹².

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectrum, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequencies of the metal-bound Schiff base in **1** are observable at ~ 1630

and $\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Compound **1** shows strong $\nu_s(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ absorptions between $2165\text{--}2220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range and two weak to medium $\nu_{\text{as}} + \nu_s(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ absorptions in the $2230\text{--}2315 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range; the shift of frequency values as compared to those of free dca ($2179, 2232$ and 2286 cm^{-1})¹³ is presumably due to bridging ($\mu_{1,5}$) coordination of the dca. Bands corresponding to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu_s(\text{C}-\text{N})$ stretching vibrations of dca are found at $\sim 1340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The compound exhibit a distinct strong and broad absorption band at $\sim 520 \text{ nm}$ due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition in its electronic spectrum in MeCN solution, which is characteristic of distorted octahedral cobalt(II) center¹⁴. The band at $\sim 295 \text{ nm}$ may be assigned to a ligand-based charge transfer transition¹⁵.

Crystal structure of **1** :

X-Ray structural analysis reveals that **1** crystallizes in the orthorhombic unit cell with $P2(1)2(1)2(1)$ space group. Perspective views of the fundamental unit with atom numbering scheme, 2D sheet structure and 3D network structure of **1** are shown in Figs. 1-3. Selected bond lengths and angles relevant to the coordination spheres are listed in Table 1. Each cobalt(II) center in the polymeric framework adopts an octahedral geometry with a CoN_6 chro-

Table 1. Bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances			
Co1-N1	2.125(4)	Co1-N5	2.081(5)
Co1-N2	2.200(3)	Co1-N6	2.086(5)
Co1-N3	2.147(4)		
Co1-N4	2.063(4)		
Bond angles			
N1-Co1-N3	89.96(16)	N5-Co1-N2	93.45(15)
N4-Co1-N2	168.53(15)	N6-Co1-N2	89.42(16)
N4-Co1-N5	97.07(17)	N1-Co1-N2	74.66(13)
N4-Co1-N6	95.03(17)	N3-Co1-N2	82.92(15)
N5-Co1-N6	90.53(17)	Co1-N3-C13	149.8(4)
N4-Co1-N1	94.67(16)	Co1-N4-C16	173.9(4)
N5-Co1-N1	168.01(15)	Co1-N5-C14	174.8(5)
N6-Co1-N1	90.89(16)	Co1-N6-C15	164.1(4)
N4-Co1-N3	93.05(16)	C13-N8-C15 ^a	122.0(5)
N5-Co1-N3	86.97(17)	C14-N7-C16 ^b	123.6(5)
N6-Co1-N3	171.78(17)		

Symmetry code : a = 3/2-x, 1-y, 1/2+z; b = 1-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z.

mophore ligated through pyridine N atom (N1) and imine N atom (N2) of didentate Schiff base and four nitrile N atoms (N3, N4, N5 and N6) of four different dca units. The equatorial positions are occupied by the two N atoms (N1 and N2) of the didentate end-capping ligand and two nitrile N atoms (N4 and N5) of two different $\mu_{1,5}$ -bridged

dca units, and the other two nitrile N atoms (N3 and N6) of two $\mu_{1,5}$ -bridged dca units are placed at the axial positions. Distortion from the ideal octahedral geometry is due to the asymmetric nature of the bound Schiff base and the deviations of the refine angles ($90^\circ/180^\circ$) formed at the metal center. The degree of distortion from an ideal octahedral geometry is reflected in the *equatorial* [$74.66(13)^\circ$ – $97.07(17)^\circ$] and the *axial* [$168.01(15)^\circ$ – $171.78(17)^\circ$] bond angles. The *axial* Co-N bond distances are in 2.063(4)–2.200(3) Å range whereas the *equatorial* ones, in 2.086(5)–2.147(4) Å range. The Co-N_{dca} distances lie in the range 2.063(4)–2.147(4) Å, whereas Co-N_{Ligand} bond distances, in 2.125(4)–2.200(3) Å range. In M-(N-C-N-C-N)-M linkage, the coordination of dca is in both linear and bending fashions as reflected in the bond angles [Co1-N3-C13 $149.8(4)^\circ$ and Co1-N4-C16 $173.9(4)^\circ$; Co1-N5-C14 $174.8(5)^\circ$ and Co1-N6-C15 $164.1(4)^\circ$]. The Co...Co separation across one $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca unit (N4-C16-N7-C14-N5) is 8.366 Å and other $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca unit (N3-C13-N8-C15-N6) is 8.151 Å respectively. Packing diagram of 2D sheet structure is a (4,4) layer network perpendicular to *bc* plane and a 3D network structure through $\mu_{1,5}$ -bridging motif of four dca units (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively). Each cobalt(II) atom lies in an inversion center, and is connected to four other

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of the 2D sheet structure in **1** with a (4,4) network perpendicular to *bc* plane.

Fig. 3. The mercury view of 3D network structure in **1**.

neighbouring metal(II) centers through four different $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridges.

Magnetic property :

The variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement for **1** performed in the 2–300 K temperature range shows (Fig. 4) that $\chi_M T$ (χ_M is the molar magnetic susceptibility for one Co^{II} ion) value continuously de-

Fig. 4. Plot of $\lambda_M T$ vs T for **1**. The solid line represents the best fit obtained. Inset : Plot of the reduced magnetization ($M/N\mu_B$) vs H at 2 K.

creases to $1.25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 2 K (with a small slope changes in very low temperature) from the value $3.25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 300 K indicating global antiferromagnetic (AF) interaction among the cobalt(II) centers mediated through long $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridges. An important experimental feature in almost all octahedral cobalt(II) complexes is that the $\chi_M T$ (or μ_{eff}) values at room temperature are greater than those expected for one isolated spin-only ion ($\chi_M T = 1.87 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ for a $S = 3/2$ ion), indicating an important orbital contribution¹⁶ with typical values of $\chi_M T$ to be $2.75\text{--}3.4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ ($4.7\text{--}5.2 \mu_B$). Lower values at room temperature indicate perturbation from ideal octahedral geometry¹⁷. The reduced magnetization curve, $M/N\mu_B$, at 2 K tends to $2.4 N\mu_B$ at $2 T$ (Fig. 4, inset) which is in agreement with the values reported in the literature¹⁸. Considering the spin-orbit coupling due to the ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes, exact calculations for deriving the J parameter from experimental data in all the temperature range is very difficult unless for simple complexes. For 3D networks it is impossible to deduce J from the $\chi_M T$ values as there are no available mathematical expressions. The shape of the experimental plot is due to (i) the spin-orbit coupling of the cobalt(II) ion and (ii) the small antiferromagnetic coupling created by the $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridging ligand¹⁹.

Luminescence behavior :

The photoluminescence behavior of the compound **1** was examined in solid state at room temperature. Upon excitation of the solid sample at its maximum absorption band (300 nm) an emission band (Fig. 5) centered at 429 nm along with a small peak at 457 nm is observed, which may be due to the ligand-based π - π^* transition^{20,21}.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence behavior of **1** in solid state.

Thermal behavior :

Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) was carried out to examine thermal stability of the compound. The sample made from crushed single crystals was heated between 40 and 800 °C in the static atmosphere of dinitrogen at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The TG curve (Fig. 6) shows that **1** is stable up to 225 °C. The compound loses one L and dicyanamide (obs. : 41.3%; calcd. : 42.2%) in the first step of its decomposition. The second step weight loss (obs. : 21.4%; calcd. : 22.2%) is in line with the removal of another dca moiety. The final residue may be due to one CoO unit (obs. : 7.8%; calcd. : 7.9%).

Conclusion

In summary, one new cobalt(II) dicyanamide compound (**1**) containing an *in situ* generated didentate Schiff base (L) has been isolated. X-Ray structural study reveals that the compound **1** is a 3D coordination polymer formed through $\mu_{1,5}$ -bridging motif of four dicyanamide bridging units and constitutes a new example of neutral metal or-

ganic framework (MOF). The coordination polymer is thermally stable and shows good luminescence property. A global antiferromagnetic (AF) interaction among the cobalt(II) centers mediated through long $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca bridges is revealed.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-aminopyridine (SRL, India), 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (E. Merck, India) and sodium dicyanamide (Lancaster, UK) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air at room temperature. All other chemicals and solvents used were analytical reagent (AR) grade. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectrum (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) was recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground state absorption (in MeCN) was measured with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was carried out on polycrystalline sample with a Quantum Design SQUID MPMS-XL magnetometer working in the 2–300 K range. The magnetic field was 0.1 T. The diamagnetic corrections were evaluated from Pascal's constants. Fluorescence measurements in solid state were done using Perkin-Elmer LS55 Fluorescence Spectrometer.

In situ generation of Schiff base, phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methanimine (L) :

The Schiff base ligand (L) was produced *in situ* as major product when the condensation reaction of 2-aminopyridine (ap) and 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) in 1 : 1 molar ratio was carried out in dehydrated ethanol in presence of cobalt(II)⁹. L was generated (Scheme 2) probably by the elimination of a pyridine ring followed by protonation. The formation of L is further ensured by X-ray crystallographic study of the complex.

*Synthesis of [Co(L)($\mu_{1,5}$ -dca)]_n (**1**) :*

To a CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.365 g, 1 mmol) solution in MeOH (10 mL), 2-aminopyridine (0.094 g, 1 mmol) and 2-

Scheme 2. Probable steps *in situ* reaction to afford L in **1**.

benzoylpyridine (0.183 g, 1 mmol) dissolved each in the same solvent (10 mL) were added dropwise. To this solution mixture, a solution of Na(dca) (0.178 g, 2 mmol) in the same solvent (10 mL) was added dropwise. After filtration through a fine glass frit, the supernatant red-dish-orange solution was kept in air for slow evaporation. Orange crystals of **1** that deposited within a week, were separated by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.30 g (70%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}N_8Co$ (**1**) : C, 51.3; H, 3.0; N, 29.9. Found : C, 51.0; H, 3.2; N, 29.7%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(C=N)$ 1630, 1590; $\nu_{as} + \nu_s(C\equiv N)$ 2312; $\nu_{as}(C\equiv N)$ 2261, 2250; $\nu_s(C\equiv N)$ 2218, 2182; $\nu_{as}(C-N)$ 1340; $\nu_s(C-N)$ 950; UV-Vis (λ ,

nm) : 520, 295.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Single crystal of **1** suitable for X-ray analyses was selected from those obtained by open evaporation of MeOH solution of the reaction mixtures at 298 K. Crystallographic data were collected on a Bruker KAPPA APEX II CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated $MoK\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 296(2) K. The detector frames were integrated by the use of the program SAINT²² and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS²³. Of the 19450 total reflections for the complex **1**, 2848, with $[I > 2\sigma(I)]$ were used for structures solutions. The structure was solved by direct methods

using SHELXTL²⁴. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions where possible and given isotropic *U* values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bonded. Materials for publication were prepared using SHELXL-2013²⁵, SHELXTL, PLATON²⁶, Mercury 3.3²⁷ and ORTEP-32²⁸ programs.

Table 2. Crystallographic data and structure refinement for **1**

Chemical formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₈ Co
Formula mass	374.26
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	P2(1)2(1)2(1)
<i>a</i> (Å)	8.506(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.736(7)
<i>c</i> (Å)	15.635(9)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	90.00
γ (°)	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1693.8(16)
λ (Å)	0.71073
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.472
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.030
<i>F</i> (000)	762
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.22 × 0.20 × 0.20
θ ranges (°)	2.06 to 24.70
<i>h</i> / <i>k</i> / <i>l</i>	-9,9/-14,14/-18,18
Reflections collected	19450
<i>T</i> _{max} and <i>T</i> _{min}	0.814 and 0.737
Data/restraints/parameters	2848/0/226
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.046
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0422
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	0.0580
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.273 and -0.519
Weighting scheme : $R = \frac{\sum F_o - F_c }{\sum F_o }$, $wR = \frac{[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}}{2}$, Calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (xP)^2 + yP]$; $x = 0.0444$ and $y = 0.5690$; where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

A summary of the crystallographic data and structure determination parameters of this complex is given in Table 2.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data

Center Nos. 1453289 (**1**). Copies of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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